

Digitization of Library Information Resources a Predictors of Conservation of Archives in Academic Libraries Universities in South- South, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: This study investigates the digitization of library information resources as a predictor of archive conservation in academic libraries across universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Method: A survey research design was adopted, guided by three research questions and three hypotheses. A stratified and purposive sampling technique selected 874 staff from six public universities, representing 10% of the total population to ensure manageability and reduce response bias. Data were collected using a validated questionnaire titled "Digitalization of Library Information Resources and Conservation of Archives Scale" (DLISCAS), with reliability coefficients ranging from 0.78 to 0.88, confirmed by Cronbach Alpha. Data analysis employed simple regression and independent t-test techniques.

Findings/Results: The digitization of newspaper collections and student project/thesis reports significantly influences archive conservation in academic libraries. No gender differences were observed in staff perceptions of digitization.

Implications: Digitization enhances the preservation and accessibility of library materials, supporting long-term conservation and broader usage of academic archives.

Conclusion: Digitization of library resources is a critical strategy for conserving archives, ensuring their longevity and accessibility in academic libraries.

Recommendations: Libraries should digitize new collections and other materials to enhance preservation and access. Students should submit final research copies in both hard and soft formats to facilitate electronic transmission and improve conservation.

Keyword: Digitization, Information Resources, Conservation, Archives, Preservation

Introduction

Academic libraries offer a wide array of information resources, encompassing both print and digital formats, including books, journals, databases, and more, to support academic research and learning. These resources are vital for students, faculty, and researchers, providing the materials they need to study, conduct research, and develop their knowledge in various fields. Information resources in academic libraries are in the print and non-print format. Information in the print format include books, maps, theses, conference papers, handbooks, dictionaries etc. while on the other hand, Information in the non-print format includes databases, journal articles and those on the website and other digital storage media.

Moses and Genevieve (2023) stated that digital information resources include online databases and e-journals. Therefore digital resources are information that can be accessed via a computer network. Information resources among the materials found in the library are mainly to serve the library users for the purpose of satisfying their information needs. Information resources as the summation of all carriers of information of diverse areas/needs which the library provides for her clientele. Use of information resources is concerned with the exploitation of

variety of information resources in the academic environment. Such resources include print, non- print and electronic materials such as online books, journals, theses, and dissertations, online newspapers, magazines, indexes/abstracts, online databases, online encyclopaedia and dictionaries etc. The emergence of digitization has revolutionized the way information resources are preserved in libraries and information centres. It has greatly enhanced information accessibility, saves time, and reduce costs. Institutions are not only able to store large amount of information but can also have quick access to information in other areas.

Abdulsalami, Nwachukwu, and Paulina, (2015) opined that digitization has enabled librarians to carry out their mandate of information capture, preservation, conservation and dissemination. There is an increase in the amount of information resources created and generated and considering the speed at which they are created their conservation becomes a challenge for most institutions. Conservation of library resources refers to the process of extending the lifespan of library materials by preventing deterioration and damage. Conservation therefore, is the treatment of library materials to stabilize their physical structure in order to sustain their survival as long as possible in their original format. This involves a variety of techniques, including proper storage, handling, and treatment of books, documents, and other resources. Preservation of resources in the library is to allow continued access, use and easy retrieval of information resources for present, future use and to protect them against threats for as long as possible. Without an effective digital preservation of information resources in libraries, access via digital devices will produce little or no resources of research, teaching and learning in the library.

Archive conservation involves preserving materials in a stable, accessible state for long-term use. This includes controlling environmental factors like temperature and humidity, using archival storage materials, and providing safe handling and storage. It also includes repairing and restoring damaged records, with all treatments documented. Digital archiving ensures that valuable digital information remains accessible and usable over time by implementing strategies and policies to address challenges like media failure and technological obsolescence. It involves planning, resource allocation, and the application of preservation methods

and technologies to ensure access to digital content. This includes both "born-digital" content and materials that have been digitized. Digital Preservation is the active management and maintenance of digital objects (the files, or groups of files, that contain information in digital form) so they can be accessed and used by future users. Digital preservation can be seen as the process and activities which stabilize and protect digital resources and publications in forms which are retrievable, readable and usable over time.

Digital preservation is the conservation of all digital materials, whether they were born digital, such as emails, websites, videogames, and other electronic files, or whether they have been digitized from analog materials asserted that digital preservation is the maintenance of objects close to their original conditions as far as possible until they are no longer needed. Unlike the preservation of paper or microfilm, digital objects demands special equipments for migration, conversion, storage, retrieval, transmission and it is continuous and ongoing. Digital preservation can therefore be seen as the set of processes and activities that ensure the continued access to information. This assertion is supported by Agidi and Gbamwuan (2023) who reported that, digital preservation refers to series of managed activities designed to ensure continuing access to resources in digital formats for as long as possible and to protect them from media failure, physical loss and obsolescence. Digital preservation of information resources can be done in either of two ways; that is the passive way and active preservation way.

The federal university libraries in South-South, Nigeria are now in the process of converting their information resources from hard copy to soft copy. The aim of a university library is to acquire process, store, preserve and disseminate information resources that are used to support teaching, learning and research for present and future generation. The researcher observed that some of the local contents such as thesis and dissertation in these institutions are mostly are in hard copies and on acidic based papers which deteriorate over time and therefore does not guarantee continuous access to information resources. Even after the information resources are digitized, continuous access to those resources would pose serious challenges therefore; there must be effective and efficient management to ensure that digital information resources are easily accessible, retrievable and re-useable for both the

present and future generation. While Kyrian, (2018) state that changes in software and hardware are some of the dangers faced in the preservation of digital information resources because these media are designed to meet up with a compatible hardware, software, and operating system and storage devices. For digital information resources created to be accessed and used continuously in the present and future generation, the hardware and software must be compatible.

Okeke, Udem, and Onwurah, (2015). stated that digital information resources are vulnerable to loss and destruction, deteriorate rapidly and can fail due to virus, exposure to heat, humidity, faulty reading and writing devices. Therefore, the federal university libraries have the responsibility to ensure that the digitized information resources are easily accessible, retrievable and re-useable for both the present and future generation as supported by Japan (2018), stated that digitization is the creation of multimedia database enhanced by digital information and thus offering easy access to cultural and scientific change for large population of users. The university libraries as centres of learning and research have over the years increased in demand of digital information resources by users, but continuous access and retrieval becomes difficult which poses serious challenge to users of such resources. It is in view of this that the researcher decided to embark on this study on digitization of library and information resources a predator to conservation of archives in academic libraries in South- South, Nigeria with the aim of ensuring effective, efficient, easy retrieval and access to the digital information resources in the academic libraries and archival institutions.

Literature Review

Digitizing and preserving information resources on national archive involves transforming physical books, newspaper, project/theses etc into digital formats, ensuring long-term accessibility and preservation. This process reduces physical wear and tear, enhances access, and allows for easier search and retrieval of information. Mommoh and Abubakar. (2019) are of the opinion that digitalizing information resources, is a process where print resources are converted to digital formats, plays a significant role in the conservation of archives in academic libraries. It not only enhances accessibility and preservation but also

offers new avenues for research and engagement with historical materials. Yes, the digitalization of information resources does indeed predict the conservation of archives in academic libraries. Orim, (2018) observed that digitization allows for the creation of high-quality copies of original materials, reducing the need for frequent handling and exposure to the elements, thereby prolonging the life of fragile items. It also enables wider access to resources, potentially reducing the need for physical access to originals, which can lead to wear and tear. Digitizing and conserving newspapers in national archives involves creating digital copies of physical newspapers for long-term preservation and public access. This process includes scanning, quality control, and metadata tagging, followed by secure storage and online availability. However, Adogbeji¹ and Akporhonor, (2021) assert that even as digital libraries enhances long term preservation in it content and collection: one major challenge with regard to metadata is the diversity of digital formats and the way they should be described in different collections with different target audience and uses. This is because in the electronic environment institutions and individuals license access to content, they do not own the containers that surround the content.

Newspaper digitization is the process of converting old newspapers from analog form into digital images. The most common analog forms for old newspapers are paper and microfilm. Digitized images of newspaper pages are typically (though not always) analyzed with OCR software in order to produce text files of the newspaper content. Newspaper digitization is a special case of digitization in general. Newspapers preserve a rich record of the past, and since the advent of digital media, many institutions across the world have begun to digitize them and make the digital files publicly available. Digitized newspapers may be made available for free or for a fee. Several lists (noted below) try to catalog digitized newspapers worldwide. Digitizing and preserving serial materials in a national archive helps ensure the long-term accessibility and integrity of valuable historical documents. Digitization creates digital surrogates, protecting fragile originals from handling and making them accessible to a wider audience. Preservation strategies involve creating digital masters, managing digital data, and ensuring the continued usability of these records.

Conservation is a more specialized field involving hands-on interventions to repair, stabilize, and restore materials that have suffered damage or decay. Trained conservators use their expertise to repair torn pages, mend broken bindings, remove harmful residues, and address other physical and chemical issues that threaten the longevity of the items. Conservation treatments aim to balance the need for repair with preserving the object's historical and aesthetic qualities. Both preservation and conservation play vital roles in ensuring library materials remain accessible and usable for current and future generations. These practices uphold the cultural heritage contained within libraries, promote scholarship and research, and contribute to the broader dissemination of knowledge. In a world increasingly reliant on digital information, preservation and conservation efforts are essential to safeguarding the tangible artifacts that connect us to our past and enrich our understanding of the human experience.

Kaye (1995) categorized the typology of information sources into format, status and location. By format we mean the physical attribute of the materials and this require further categorization into paper based sources, oral or audio sources, electronic sources, textual sources and media sources. Status refers to such sources as personal, formal or informal sources, published/unpublished sources and open/secret or confidential sources. Location means where the information is generated or could be obtained such as internal or external. Whatever is the source of information in a library it must be one which could be used by the users because the major objective of the library is to facilitate use of information? Modern libraries according to Adogbeji and Akporhonor (2021) are developed to process and access books and other reading materials, hence the need to preserve the resources through digitization for future use. But the decision to digitalize any material in the library must be based on the physical size of the nature and condition of the source of the material. That is the characteristics of the product to be digitalized. It must also be ascertained that the available means of conversion can bring out result in the project. Above all the product must specify how users could be guided to use it. Understanding the source of materials which constitute the library's collection is also another important consideration which must be given in any digitization project. For example sources /materials include: project reports, staff publications, working papers, thesis, manuals and handbooks, audio and video, printings and

photograph collection, historical documents, songs and musical scores, oral history etc. Digitization involves the step taken to preserve information resources by converting printed information materials into electronic digital format with a view to making the resources accessible. This activity is undertaken by acquiring the material to be digitalized, scanning the materials to transcribe it into digital format, and by creating mark up and index to create Metadata. To ensure quality control of this activity, specialist is required to handle the activities and to process the images.

Digitization in library is undertaken with a view to preserve and maintains the collection of the library. It has been observed that many items in the collection of the library are deteriorating fast due to heavy usage. Many documents are also missing due to perhaps anti-social behavior of some of the users. Therefore, to ensure that the library fulfill its obligation to the users, preservation through digitization is undertaken. But the issue at stake is how the user will benefit from this laudable action. Perhaps the materials being digitized are not relevant to the users due to selection problems when trying to identify the items to be digitized. Perhaps also the users do not know how to use the digitized information resources due to lack of knowledge on how to operate the computer which is the machine gain reception from the digitized resources. It is in line with this that a study set to examine the influence digitalization of library information resources on conservation of archives in academic. The study will also examine the rate at which the digitalized resources are being used by the users and how library staff in charge of digitization could improve the practice in the library.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to examine the influence digitalization of library information resources on conservation of archives in academic libraries in South-South Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to find out whether:

- i. Digitalization of newspaper collections predicts the conservation of archives in academic libraries.
- ii. Digitalization of student's projects/thesis predicts the conservation of archives in academic libraries

- iii. There exist gender differences on staff perception to the digitalization of library information system

Research questions ‘

The following research questions were raised to guide the study

- i. How does digitalization of newspaper collections predict the conservation of archives in academic libraries
- ii. How does digitalization of student’s projects/thesis predict the conservation of archives in academic libraries
- iii. To what extent do male and female staff differ on their perception to the digitalization of library information system

Statement of hypotheses

The hypotheses were stated in the null form as followed

- i. Digitalization of newspaper collections does no significantly predict the conservation of archives in academic libraries
- ii. Digitalization of student’s projects/thesis does no significantly predict the conservation of archives in academic libraries
- iii. There is no significant differences between male and female staff perception to the digitalization of library information resources in academic libraries

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design with a stratified and purpose sampling technique to select 874 staff from six public universities in South -South. Each of the stratum such as university of Calabar, university of Porhacourt, University of Uyo. Federal university of petroleum Efurum university of Benin and Federal university Otueke. In each of the stratum, 10% of the respondents were selected for the study. Simple random sampling techniques was further applied to ensure that all respondents have equal opportunity of been represented. This helped to select the sample that is used for the study. The use of a 10% sample allows for the collection of data that is sufficiently representative of the larger population while remaining manageable in terms of time, cost, and available resources (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). Moreover, this proportion aligns with practices in similar cross-

sectional studies where researchers aim to balance statistical validity with logistical feasibility. Given the constraints typically associated with field research—such as limited personnel, funding, and access—adopting a 10% sample provides a reliable foundation for generalizing findings within the study context (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The instrument was validated by experts in Measurement and Evaluation and the reliability was ascertained using Cronbach Alpha and the coefficient of the sub scale ranged from 0.78-0.88 which was adjudged to be high. Data collection was done by the researcher and data collected analysed using simple regression technique and independent t-test analysis and the result is presented below

Presentation of result /discussion of findings

Hypothesis one

Digitalization of newspaper collections does not significantly predict the conservation of archives in academic libraries. The independent variable in this hypothesis is digitalization of newspaper collections while the dependent variable is conservation of archives in academic libraries, all measured continuously. To test this hypothesis, simple regression analysis was used and the result as presented in Table 1 showed that $R = 0.645$ which implies that there is a strong positive relationship between digitalization of newspaper collections and conservation of archives in academic libraries. That is, the higher the digitalized newspaper collections are, the more conserved archives are in the libraries. More so, the $Adj R^2 = 0.400$ showed that the variations in conservation of archives in academic libraries could be explained using 40.0% contribution of digitalization of newspaper collections. Furthermore, a careful look at the analysis of variance (ANOVA) result showed that ($F = 88.38, p < .05$). Since $p(.000)$ is less than $p(.05)$, this implies that there is a significant influence of digitalization of newspaper collections on conservation of archives in academic libraries in South-South and South East Nigeria. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate which stated that there is a significant influence of digitalization of newspaper collections on conservation of archives in academic libraries retained.

TABLE 1: Simple regression analysis of the influence digitalization of newspaper collection on conservation of archives

Source of variation	Sun of squares	df	Mean squares	f-ratio	p-value
Between	1009.14	1	1009.14		
Within	9906.68	872	11.36	88.83	.000
Total	10915.82	873			

R=0.654, R² = 0.427, Adj. R² = 0.400,

Hypothesis two

Digitalization of student projects/thesis does no significantly predict the conservation of archives in academic libraries. The independent variable in this hypothesis is digitalization of student projects/thesis while the dependent variable is conservation of archives in academic libraries, all measured continuously. To test this hypothesis, simple regression analysis was used and the result as presented in Table 2 showed that R= 0.881which implies that there is a strong positive relationship between digitalization of student projects/thesis and conservation of archives in academic libraries.

That is, the higher the digitalized student projects/thesis are, the more conserved archives are in the libraries. More so, the Adj R² =0.710showed that the variations in conservation of archives in academic libraries could be explained 71.0% contribution of digitalization of student projects/thesis. Furthermore, a careful look at the analysis of variance (ANOVA) result showed that (F=103.88, p<.05). Since p(.000) is less than p(.05), this implies that there is a significant influence of digitalization of student projects/thesis on conservation of archives in academic libraries in South-South and South East Nigeria. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate which stated that there is a significant influence of digitalization of student projects/thesis on conservation of archives in academic libraries retained

Table 2: Simple regression analysis of the influence digitalization of students' projects/thesis on conservation of archives

Source of variation	Sun of squares	df	Mean squares	f-ratio	p-value
Between	1198.87	1	1198.87		
Within	9716.96	872	11.14	107.61	.000
Total	10915.82	873			

R=0.881, R² = 0.776, Adj. R² = 0.710,

Hypothesis three

There is no significant difference between male and female staff perception on the digitalization of library information resources in academic libraries. The independent variable is gender categorized as male and female while the dependent variable is digitalization of library information resources in academic libraries. To test this hypothesis, independent t-test was used and the result as presented in Table 3 showed that (t=-1.08, p>.05). Since p(.761) is greater than p(.05), this implies that there is no significant difference between male and female staff perception on the digitalization of library information resources in academic libraries. Hence, the null hypothesis is retained.

Table 3: Independent t-test analysis of the influence of gender on digitalization of library information resources in academic libraries

Variables	N	Mean	Std Dev	df	t-cal	p-val
Male	401	14.76	4.98	872	-1.08	.761
Female	473	14.87	4.76			

Discussion of findings

Hypothesis one that stated that; there is no significant influence of digitalization of newspapers collection on conservation of archives was rejected. This implies that digitalization of newspapers collection on conservation of archives could be due to the fact that, newspapers which serves as one of the means of information has been grossly abused over time is but with electronic tools, it can aid in retrieval and usage at any time. Information loss which was experienced of recent will no longer

be the issue. The finding of the study is in line with that of Toyo (2017) research that investigated the impacts of library resources digitization on the services of academic libraries using John Harris Library, University of Benin, Benin City. The major findings revealed the following: the major reasons for the digitization of library resources at John Harris Library include the need to preserve library resources for long use and to have better search and retrieval facilities for library materials; that the main benefits of digitizing library resources are that digitization enables greater access to collections of all types and give the ability to search for library resources electronically without difficulties among others; that the impacts of digitized library resources on the services of academic libraries include helping to offer more online services to library users and providing quick and easy methods of delivering services to them and that that there are many challenges facing digitization of library resources in academic libraries. The study also showed that digitalization of library resources influence conservation and preservation of library resources. However, Adogbeji¹ and Akporhonor, (2021) had a contrary view that digital content and collection is of one major challenge where metadata is the diversity of digital formats and the way they should be described in different collections with different target audience and uses. This is because in the electronic environment institutions and individuals license access to content, they do not own the containers that surround the content.

Hypothesis two that stated that there is no significant influence of digitalization of student project and thesis collection on conservation of archives was rejected. This implies that digitalization of student project and thesis collection on conservation of archives. This could be due to the fact that most times, students project and thesis report is the most abused information in academic libraries yet much is used in those works. They serve as referral point in most research works that are carried out. The dumping of these records on ground, field among other areas talks more about the conservative nature of the system. The digitalization these records may help the students in future research works. The finding of the study is in line with that of Yusuf (2019) whose study is to investigate the digitalization of resources in academic libraries. The findings of the study showed that digitalization of student's works and other collection influences conservation of resources in libraries, which also corroborate with the view of Mommoh and Abubakar. (2019) state that

digitalizing information resources, is a process where print resources are converted to digital formats, plays a significant role in the conservation of archives in academic libraries. However, their view were at variants with Adogbeji¹ and Akporhonor, (2021) who assert that creating a digital library is a very expensive venture which requires adequate planning and monitoring. The major problem is lack of technical-know-how; hence most digitization projects often run into problems.

Hypothesis three, stated that there is no gender difference in staff perception of digitalization of library information resources was retained. This implies that male and female staff does not differ in their perception of digitalization of library information resources this could be due to the fact that both staff recognizes the relevance of electronizing information in this era and thus, supportive of the use of digital technologies in the library. The findings of the study is in tandem with Olaniyi Popoola and Olawale, (2024) that carried out a study on demographic factors as correlates of digital information resources use by is doctoral students in Southwestern Nigeria; The findings showed that there is no gender difference, age and educational differences in staff perception of digitalization of library information resources.

Conclusion /recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that digitalization of newspaper collections, student's project/thesis report influences conservation of archives in academic libraries. More so, there is no gender difference in the perception of staff on digitalization of library information resources. Based on the conclusion, it was recommended that

- i. New collections and other materials in the library should be digitalized in order to help preserve and conserve these materials for wider access and usage
- ii. Student should be made to submit their final research copy on hard disk and soft disk to aid to transmission of the soft copy electronically of better conservation.

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